

Propionic Acid-based Additive on Aerobic Stability of Total Mixed Ration – I: Dairy Cows Performance and Feed Frequency

Ariadna Patricia Ribeiro¹, Álvaro Bernardo da Silva Neto¹, Juliana Machado¹, Bruno Augusto Valverde Arthur¹, Leandro Greco², Greiciele Moraes¹, and Luiz Gustavo Nussio¹

¹ESALQ Department of Animal Science, University of São Paulo, Piracicaba, SP, Brazil

²Kemin Industries, Brazil

Keywords: aerobic stability, dairy cows, feeding frequency, total mixed ration.

Introduction

Tropical climates present environmental challenges to the stability of total mixed ration (TMR) in the feed bunk throughout the day. Increasing feeding frequency is a typical suggested strategy to compensate for TMR deterioration and to prevent refusal by animals. However, treatment with a propionic acid-based additive could stabilize the TMR enough to allow a reduction in daily feeding frequency.

Materials and methods

A preliminary trial was performed to select the most effective dose of the additive (Fresh Cut™ Plus, Kemin South America, Brazil) based on the monitoring of the aerobic stability of TMR. Data was analyzed as a completely randomized design including fixed effect of dose, and means were compared by polynomial regression ($p \leq 0.05$). The additive was effective on improving aerobic stability of TMR compared to the control treatment. However, there was no difference across doses starting from 2 mL/kg fresh matter (FM) (Table 1). Our results suggested the dose of 2 mL/kg FM as the most effective for improvement of the aerobic stability of TMR, and this dose was selected for the Additive strategy in the animal performance trial. Twelve Holstein cows (mean \pm SD; 612 \pm 158 kg of body weight, 27 \pm 6.5 kg/d milk yield, 178 \pm 60 days in milk, and 3.0 \pm 0.5 of body condition score) were assigned to a switch-back design to evaluate the effect of two feeding management strategies: Control, with two daily feedings of a control TMR; and Additive, with cows receiving a single daily feeding of a TMR treated with the additive at 2 L/t FM. The TMR was composed of 44.59% corn silage, 6.40% Tifton wilted silage, 21.11% rehydrated corn grain silage, 9.25% citrus pulp, 16.33% soybean meal and 2.32% mineral-vitamin mix. The animals were housed in a free-stall barn equipped with individual feed bunks, capable of individual access control and feeding behavior monitoring system (Intergado Ltda., Contagem, Minas Gerais, Brazil). The cows were subjected to two daily milkings, at 5 am and 5 pm. At the afternoon feed delivery for the Control diet, the TMR was manually mixed in the feed bunks for both treatments throughout three minutes, immediately before the animals had access to it, in order to stimulate consumption randomly. The parameters of animal performance included fixed effect of treatment, random effect of period (1, 2, 3), and random effect of animal. All statistical analyses were made using the MIXED procedure of SAS 9.4 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC).

Results

Cows fed the Additive strategy significantly increased daily milk yield by 10.2% without changes in dry matter intake, although no difference was observed for the feed efficiency (Table 2). Milk fat content was decreased for cows in the Additive strategy. An increase in milk somatic cell counts was observed for cows in the Additive, which could be related to the faster first meal activity after milking than the cows in the Control strategy, rendering them more susceptible to teat contamination. Milk energy and milk urea nitrogen contents were not affected by treatments, although energy excretion through milk was greater for the cows in the Additive. The Additive strategy promoted a shift in the sorting behavior in favor of longer particles, increasing the time spent on rumination, and decreased the number of daily meals at the expense of larger meal size.

Conclusions

The treatment of TMR with the propionic acid-based additive improved its aerobic stability and enabled the strategy of a single daily feeding to dairy cows with an increased milk yield by 10.2% and rumination time by 9.7%. The additive-treated TMR promoted a shift in the sorting behavior in favor of longer particles, increasing the time spent on rumination, and decreased the number of daily meals (31.5%) at the expense of larger meal size (21.4%), without changes in dry matter intake. Cows fed the Additive TMR also spent less time with first meal post-milking, resulting in higher SCC.

References

Dias, M.S.S., Ghizzi, L.G., Marques, J.A., Nunes, A.T., Grigoletto, N.T.S., Gheller, L.S., Silva, T.B.P., Silva, G.G., Lobato, D.N., Costa e Silva, L.F., and Rennó, F.P. 2021. Effects of organic acids in total mixed ration and feeding frequency on productive performance of dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 104:5405-5416. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2020-19419>.

Gheller, L.S., Ghizzi, L.G., Marques, J.A., Takiya, C.S., Grigoletto, N.T.S., Dias, M.S.S., Silva, T.B.P., Nunes, A.T., Da Silva, G.G., Fernandes, L.G.X., Rennó, L.N., and Rennó, F.P. 2021. Effects of organic acid-based products added to total mixed ration on performance and ruminal fermentation of dairy cows. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 261:114–406. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2020.114406>.

Table 1. Preliminary aerobic stability trial of total mixed ration.

Item	Additive dose (/kg FM)						SEM	L	Q	D
	0 mL	1 mL	2 mL	3 mL	4 mL	5 mL				
Aerobic stability, h	47.8	53.0	73.8	73.5	74.1	75.4	3.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.11
T_{max}, °C	41.2	39.4	38.2	38.3	38.2	27.0	0.00	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
TT_{max}, h	170.0	169.3	169.1	168.8	169.0	145.8	2.28	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

T_{max} – maximum temperature; TT_{max} – time to achieve maximum temperature.

Table 2. Performance of dairy cows fed the experimental total mixed rations.

Item	Treatment		SEM	P-value
	Additive	Control		
Dry matter intake, kg/d	22.3	21.6	0.89	0.59
Milk, kg/d	25.9	23.5	1.34	0.01
Feed efficiency	1.22	1.15	0.08	0.42
Energy-corrected milk, kg/d	25.1	23.2	1.16	0.03
Fat, %	3.28	3.41	0.07	0.01
Crude Protein, %	3.26	3.26	0.06	0.92
Lactose, %	4.44	4.48	0.03	0.06
Milk NE_L, Mcal/kg	0.66	0.67	0.01	0.12
NE_L, Mcal/d	16.8	15.6	0.77	0.04
Somatic cell count, mil/mL	99.3	41.8	8.10	<0.01
Milk urea nitrogen, mg/dL	12.5	13.1	0.27	0.27
Particle sorting index, % as fed				
> 19 mm	114.3	84.2	3.53	<0.01
8-19 mm	97.2	101.4	0.66	<0.01
4-8 mm	98.3	98.8	0.72	0.76
< 4 mm	98.6	102.4	0.73	<0.01
Ingesting, min/d	188	258	9.2	<0.01
Ruminating, min/d	599	546	10.1	<0.01
Idleness, min/d	625	621	12.6	0.82
Water intake, min/d	27	21	2.1	0.05
Meal frequency, meals/d	6.1	8.9	0.27	<0.01
Meal size, kg	3.4	2.8	0.19	0.03
Meal length, min	20.0	20.8	1.00	0.49
1st meal (morning feeding), kg	4.4	4.4	0.32	0.84
1st meal (morning feeding), min	21.7	32.3	2.21	<0.01
1st meal (afternoon feeding), kg	3.7	3.4	0.29	0.42

1st meal (afternoon feeding), min	20.3	28.0	2.02	<0.01
---	------	------	------	-------

Contact Information: Luiz Gustavo Nussio, Email: nussio@usp.br